

UNIVERSITY OF
BIRMINGHAM

Research Software Group

Advanced Research Computing

Annual Report
2023

Contents

Advanced Research Computing	3
Research Software Group	5
RSE Service	6
RSE Data Science Service	11
BEAR Apps	13
Case Studies	15
Training	22
Conferences and Events	24
Contact Us	29

Advanced Research Computing

BEAR

BIRMINGHAM ENVIRONMENT FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH

Advanced Research Computing (ARC) designs, operates and supports a range of services for researchers at the University of Birmingham and beyond.

Birmingham researchers benefit from ARC's award winning Birmingham Environment for Academic Research (BEAR). These BEAR ser-

VICES are designed to support research and many are free at the point of use. More than three thousand research projects with over five thousand staff and students are currently registered to use BEAR services. Since starting to collect the data in 2021, our academics have told us about over a thousand publications that resulted in full or in part from using BEAR.

Baskerville is a national accelerated compute system funded by EPSRC and UKRI, and (like BEAR) routinely receives excellent feedback from researchers who use it. Baskerville is available to researchers requiring GPU-acceleration from the Baskerville consortium partners (which includes University of Birmingham), and from the wider UK research community via EPSRC's Access to HPC calls.

ARC is based in IT Services, led by Carol Sandys and reporting to the Chief Information Officer, Mark Gee. The Team has grown substantially over recent years, and now has over 30 members. The University's commitment to BEAR was reasserted in the most recent Vice Chancellor's Review of IT Services and in the Digital Strategy, and our services continue to expand to meet the needs of the research community.

ARC comprises three groups:

- Architecture, Infrastructure and Systems Group
- Research Engagement and Data Group
- Research Software Group

These groups provide experts to design and operate ARC's compute, storage and related services and also specialists at engaging with and supporting our wide and varied community of researchers.

The report that follows provides an introduction to the work of the Research Software Group and gives brief case studies to illustrate the benefits partnership with the RSG, and ARC, can deliver.

Carol Sandys

Head of Advanced Research Computing and Research Engagement

Research Software Group

The Research Software Group (RSG) is part of Advanced Research Computing at the University of Birmingham. The RSG has grown substantially since it was formed in 2017. At the end of 2023 the team has 18 members, split into three job types:

- Research Applications Specialists - who support users of BEAR's high performance computing services BlueBEAR, BEAR Cloud and Baskerville. A significant part of this work is installing, curating and supporting over a thousand applications and libraries available on these systems.
- Research Software Engineers - who join research projects or groups for longer-term funded collaborations. They also provide free advice, coaching and coding work for any University researcher, from PhD students to senior academics.
- Research Data Scientists - who all joined the team in 2023 and together have launched our new Research Data Science Service. They facilitate data intensive research by providing specialist data science support and advice.

The RSG's mission is summed up in the words of the Software Sustainability Institute: “better software, better research”.¹ To help us achieve this mission we are currently recruiting several new posts, and by mid-2024 the team should have 25 members.

The Research Software Group exists to:

- Enable the University of Birmingham's research community to get the best from their research software
- Provide specialist software engineering and data science advice and support to researchers
- Help to enhance the University's reputation for high quality research
- Help researchers get the most from BEAR services, maximising the return on the University's investment in BEAR

¹ <https://www.software.ac.uk/resources/publications/better-software-better-research>

RSE Service

Research Software Engineers

The term 'Research Software Engineer' (RSE) was coined in March 2012 at the Collaborations Workshop and you can find all about the history of RSEs from the State of the Nation report from 2017² and 'A not-so-brief history of Research Software Engineers'³.

RSEs use software engineering practices to develop and support software in research applications. They focus on reproducibility, reusability, and accuracy of data analysis and applications created for research. RSEs are frequently multi-skilled and adaptable, turning their hands to anything from coaching researchers in data science, optimising high-throughput data pipelines, developing full-stack web applications, or implementing AI models on supercomputers - anything really that helps researchers do better research. All of the RSEs at ARC have a wide variety of technical skills and most have been researchers at some point in their careers.

The value of good Research Software Engineering

Research software engineering covers a broad spectrum of applications and good Research Software Engineering principles result in more reproducible and accurate research.

Our RSE engagements are always collaborative - with the RSE and researchers working together. The need for this is highlighted by the following quote from the Government Office for Science:

'Domain scientists need to have the relevant skills to be able to map scientific problems to computational solutions. It is also important that they work closely with RSEs and other computing professionals to produce efficient and reliable software.'⁴

² Brett, A., Croucher, M., Haines, R., Hettrick, S., Hetherington, J., Stillwell, M., & Wyatt, C. (2017). Research Software Engineers: State of the Nation Report 2017. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.495360>

³ Simon Hettrick. (2016). A not-so-brief history of Research Software Engineers. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076740>

⁴ Government Office for Science. (2021). Large-scale computing: the case for greater UK coordination, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/654a4025e2e16a000d42aaef/UK_Computing_report_-_Final_20.09.21.pdf, p63

Having an RSE (or two) on your research project is a cost effective way of increasing the quality of your research and gaining a valuable collaborator!

The Future of Compute review 'found that RSEs are increasingly leaving academia due to low salaries, short-term contracts, lack of recognition and uncertain career progression'⁵. In this context, we have built a pool of RSEs on permanent contracts and established a career path including Grade 7 (RSE), Grade 8 (Senior RSE) and Grade 9 (Principal RSE), with the long-term support of the Pro-Vice Chancellor (Research), the Digital Research Committee, and the IT Services leadership team. Our goal is to retain and grow this valuable resource for the long-term benefit of the University research community.

RSE Service: Advice, Coaching, Coding and Mentoring

The Research Software Engineering Service (RSE Service) consists of a range of offerings to all researchers in the University. These services include advice, coaching, coding and mentoring sessions and engagements.

RSE Services are offered on a free and paid-for basis. The free services include one-off advice sessions, mentoring and short coaching or coding engagements. The paid-for services are usually funded through researchers' grants and allow for longer coaching or coding engagements, from one month to several years. Typical arrangements for funded engagements involve paying for a percentage of one or more RSEs to work on a defined project. We also offer "flexible" offerings for ongoing projects where individual work packages can be defined within an umbrella engagement.

More detail on our free, funded and flexible services can be found in following sections and on our website: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/rsg/rse-service>.

RSE Service: Free Engagements

The RSE Service offers advice and mentoring, and short coaching or coding engagements free to all researchers in the University.

Advice: We are happy to offer advice on any aspect of research software. Examples might include using version control to improve software quality, or porting to or optimising software

⁵ Department for Science, Innovation & Technology. (2023). Independent Review of The Future of Compute: Final report and recommendations. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/future-of-compute-review/the-future-of-compute-report-of-the-review-of-independent-panel-of-experts>

on a new compute platform. By following the RSE Service Advice a researcher should be able to improve the reliability and maintainability of the research software they write or use and this will help the researcher with the reproducibility and robustness of their research.

Mentoring: Researchers who code, or RSEs embedded in research groups, can often be the only person in their group with significant coding responsibilities or experience. We offer this mentoring option for those who would like to develop a longer-term relationship with the RSG. Through this mentoring relationship the mentee would develop their technical and non-technical skills as they discuss their work, career aspirations and training needs. Typically mentoring meetings take the form of an informal conversation a few times a year. Space is limited for this service and sometimes there may be a delay before a new mentoring engagement can start.

Coaching: If a researcher, or research group, has the need for specific research software expertise, then an RSE can be requested, free of charge, for multiple half-day coaching sessions (max. 10). During these sessions the RSE would meet the researcher or research group (physically or virtually) to work with them to complete specific agreed objectives. Examples might include learning a new skill, reviewing code or designing and implementing a testing framework. These tasks are typically achieved by doing pair programming or a teaching/homework model similar to PhD supervision.

Coding: If a researcher, or research group, has the need for specific research software tasks to be completed (but doesn't want or have the time for a coaching engagement) then we offer up to ten days of coding time, sometimes spread over several weeks. Examples might include re-implementing an algorithm in a different programming language, adding parallelisation or CUDA (GPU) support to an application, or developing a research web application beyond what is available in the standard UoB web offerings.

For all these engagements, we write some lightweight paperwork to agree who will do what, and when. Free follow-on engagements may be available afterwards, although there is usually a delay due to demand.

To request advice, mentoring, coaching or coding please email bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk and specify which service you would like along with some details of the work.

RSE Service: Flexible Engagements

A Flexible RSE agreement is one where a researcher funds some RSE time to be used as required, instead of over a fixed period of time. It provides a framework for individual pieces

of work which we call 'work packages'. These work packages can then be defined at any time in the life of the project, to suit the project's needs.

For example, a project might need RSE input for three months at the start of year two to help review and validate software written by the researcher before it is used in earnest in simulations or experiments. And then again, a year later to help to package and publish the software for use by third parties. Or RSEs might be called upon to run a variety of training courses or coaching sessions periodically throughout a project's life.

With suitable notice and planning the same RSEs could work on several work packages as part of a research project, spread over years. Equally, different combinations of RSEs may be more appropriate to deliver different work packages. Work packages can be all defined up front, or ad hoc throughout the life of the project. Please note that we cannot guarantee that an RSE will be available at short notice for a newly defined work package.

If you are considering including a Flexible RSE Engagement as part of a grant application please get in touch with us at an early stage by emailing bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk.

We cannot guarantee to supply grant-funded RSE time if we were not consulted prior to the bid being submitted to the funding body. Nevertheless, if you find yourself in this position do get in touch and we will try to help.

RSE Service: Funded Engagements

The RSG has a growing contingent of RSEs available for funded projects. (For example we are recruiting several more in early 2024.) In many ways the funded engagements are similar to our free engagements, but are generally longer or involve more people. RSEs can be included in grant applications or bought-out using existing research funding.

The idea is to allow a research group/project to pay for one or more RSEs with particular skills for a period of time. This could be a short project like two RSEs running a two-week workshop, or a long project for example 50% FTE for 2 years. To achieve this we have a central pool of RSEs that work on funded projects for the majority of their role.

We offer two main types of funded engagement:

- Short projects (a month or less) can have any percentage FTE of RSEs - e.g. 20% of one RSE and 90% of another for a month - depending on availability.
- Long projects (typically 3 months or more) should be defined as essentially 50% of an RSE, or multiples. For example two RSEs at 50% for 2 years. For each 50% FTE we will

actually quote 45% of the RSE, and 5% of a senior member of the RSG who will provide code review, support, mentoring and advice to the RSE. Our policy is that no RSE will work more than 45% on a single long project, so for larger requirements we will provide multiple RSEs as needed.

It is rare that an RSE engagement will have static requirements specified up front - and much more likely that the researcher and RSE will work together defining and re-defining the goals of the project as time goes on. As such we encourage you to think of RSE engagements as research collaborations, and RSEs as more like researchers than consultants.

For more detail about our funded engagements and for instructions on how to include RSEs in a Worktribe project see <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/rsg/rse-service/funded-engagements.aspx>.

If you are considering including an RSE on a grant application please get in touch with us at an early stage by emailing bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk.

We cannot guarantee to supply grant-funded RSE time if we were not consulted prior to the bid being submitted to the funding body. Nevertheless, if you find yourself in this position do get in touch and we will try to help.

RSE Data Science Service

The Research Data Science Service

The Research Data Science Service is part of the [Institute for Interdisciplinary Data Science and AI \(IIDSAI\)](#) and the Research Software Group. We aim to improve and enable state-of-the-art data science at the University through a range of complementary services. We are funded by both IIDSAI and the [Centre for Artificial Intelligence in Government \(CAIG\)](#). The service is new consisting initially of three Research Data Scientists.

Services

Our work is split into three parts:

- **Institute-funded work** which is free at point of use for researchers across the whole University. This includes pre-award work where our Research Data Scientists provide services to increase the competitiveness of funding bids and short pieces of post-award work, such as advice and coaching, where we aim to improve the quality and impact of research outputs.
- **Funded project work** where we collaborate with research groups to work on longer-term data science related research.
- **IIDSAI Pump-priming projects** which will be organised annually and enable our Research Data Scientists to work on impactful interdisciplinary and emerging projects with the explicit aim to generate further funding.

Expertise

Our expertise covers a variety of key areas, including:

- **Advanced Analytics** including statistical analysis, machine learning, and deep learning. Developing predictive models, clustering, dimensionality reduction, and the implementation of neural networks.
- **Textual Analysis**, for example natural language processing.
- **Image Analysis** covering a range of applications, including medical images such as microscopy, MEG and fMRI data.
- **Mathematical Modelling** of systems.
- **Data Visualization** including interactive dashboards to facilitate a deeper understanding of your data.

- **Data Collection and Extraction** including scraping from diverse sources, documents, APIs, and web pages.
- **Data Preparation** including cleaning and transforming raw data into analysis-ready datasets.

How We Can Help

We expect that researchers will want to enlist the Research Data Science service to:

- Access advice on applying AI and data science techniques to their data, e.g. selecting the most appropriate method considering the research question, available data, computational resources, and desired level of explainability.
- Implement statistical analyses or develop machine-learning models, while adhering to software-engineering best practices such as version control and documentation to support reproducibility and open science.

Where researchers work at the cutting edge of data science themselves, e.g. developing new algorithms or statistical methods, the data science service can help with benchmarking against existing methods and conducting simulation studies.

Our data scientists are also able to offer support in several data-science-adjacent areas, including aspects of data management and data engineering. Example tasks might include:

- Documenting and preparing a research data set for sharing.
- Scaling up a data analysis to work with larger datasets while preserving performance.

Our Contribution

Our data scientists are valuable because they (i) provide expert data science support, allowing researchers to focus on being domain experts, (ii) help speed up research through automation and addressing bottlenecks, e.g. data wrangling, (iii) help raise the quality of research through the sharing of data-science best practices, and (iv) implement the latest data-science techniques to gain new insights from research data.

What a RAS does

- Application and software support:
 - Installs software applications on the University's high performance computing (HPC) systems.
 - Compiles and optimises software packages for the HPC environment, using the [Easy-Build framework](#).
- User Support:
 - Provides comprehensive technical support to the university's researchers, assisting them in using our systems effectively and efficiently.
 - Provides application-specific support and assist users in debugging problems.
- User Training:
 - Assists the team in providing regular training to staff and research students from a variety of disciplines across the university.
- User Documentation:
 - Maintains and extends our public-facing documentation sites. These sites primarily comprise technical documentation and apply to all services provided to researchers. The documentation can be viewed at:
 - ★ <https://docs.bear.bham.ac.uk>
 - ★ <https://docs.baskerville.ac.uk>
- Internal Documentation:
 - Maintains and extends our internal wiki pages, ensuring that knowledge is shared across the team.
- Collaboration and Communication:
 - Works closely with colleagues from other groups within Advanced Research Computing as well as with staff from across IT Services.
 - Collaborates with researchers from across all areas of the University.

Case Studies

Coaching Case Study - Automating Catalyst Testing

Ammonia has the potential to be an effective way of storing hydrogen as an environmentally-friendly fuel, if it can efficiently be broken down to release the hydrogen when it's needed. The researchers are studying how efficiently new, novel catalysts can decompose ammonia, using experimental apparatus in their lab at the University of Birmingham. With manual control, they could run the experiment twice a week but partially automating it would allow them to run it more often, leading to faster results about potential catalysts.

We regularly met the researchers to discuss how to automate the equipment. The conditions were quite unusual for research software. The experimental apparatus was connected to a computer that itself had to be kept offline and the equipment would only respond to very basic inputs and outputs, often in a way that was not documented well. Together, we and the researchers steadily developed our capacity to write to and read from the devices in the experiment. Ultimately, the researchers were able to automate the experiment's shutdown phase, which can now happen safely over the weekend, speeding up their study of candidate catalysts.

The support provided to us by Warrick and Makis from the Research Software Group was invaluable towards completing the core goals of our catalytic rig automation project.

Throughout our sessions, we achieved partially-automated control of our gas rig, allowing us to significantly increase its capacity for use, as well as streamlining aspects of data collection and equipment programming. The mentoring style of engagement was especially effective in allowing me to develop and consolidate my Python skills, which has supported the ongoing development of our group's data acquisition and handling protocols, as well as the training of other group members in related coding projects.

- **Caitlin Brooker-Davis, School of Chemistry, College of Engineering and Physical Sciences**

Coaching Case Study - Delivering Baskerville Training at the Alan Turing Institute

In February 2023, three members of the RSG travelled to the Alan Turing Institute, the UK's national institute for data science and AI, to train current PhD students and other researchers on how to get the best out of the Baskerville Tier 2 HPC facility based here at the University of Birmingham. Baskerville is designed to be exclusively used for GPU-heavy tasks, such as Machine Learning, which makes it an excellent tool for our partners at the Turing.

As well as demonstrating Slurm, a common job scheduler for HPC, we also showcased Baskerville Portal which provides web-based access to software running on Baskerville. This software can be general purpose, such as JupyterLab and MATLAB, or very specific, such as the electron cryo-microscopy tool RELION. When we speak to Baskerville users, the ease of using the Portal is frequently mentioned as a reason to prefer Baskerville for HPC tasks, along with the support offered by the RSG and wider ARC.

In addition to this, we offered training on how to significantly increase the speed users can perform ETL (Extract, Transform, and Load) tasks, which are preliminary to any analysis, using GPU-accelerated software libraries.

As a result of this training, several new projects were registered on Baskerville by attendees.

The Baskerville training event was highly successful, with many attendees progressing from almost no experience with HPC to running jobs and solving problems using Baskerville. The event was not only about imparting knowledge but also provided a great opportunity to connect and share ideas. We are looking forward to future events and hope they will be just as successful as this one. Such activities not only enrich our community's expertise but also reinforces our lasting partnership with the Baskerville Tier 2 HPC facility.

- **Tomas Lazauskas, Principal Research Software Engineer, The Alan Turing Institute**

Coding Case Study - AIDA and AENeAS

A map showing the vertically-integrated electron density in the Earth's ionosphere, as inferred by the data assimilation program AIDA, at 02:15 UTC on April 24, 2023. The results are from a run requested via the user interface on the Django website developed by RSEs from the Research Software Group. The points show the locations of 4024 receivers whose observations of global navigation satellite system (GNSS) satellites are used in the assimilation.

RSEs have continued to work with the SERENE group, who have developed cutting-edge data assimilation tools for forecasting conditions in the Earth's ionosphere. These 'space weather' forecasts are invaluable for anticipating the ionosphere's effect, for example on radio communication and satellite navigation.

Over 2023, the group has deployed forecasts on the ESA Space Weather portal, which imposed tight requirements on how quickly the data assimilation has to run. The group optimised the data assimilation program, integrated the results into the ESA platform and ported the ESA data products to also be available locally. Besides the forecasts, the group also developed an interface through which users can request data assimilation runs of past ionospheric activity, to infer the complete state of the ionosphere using all the data that subsequently became available. The RSEs developed a new package to assemble the wide variety of data from dozens of data providers worldwide that can be used in these runs.

The RSEs have also started improving a newer data assimilation tool, AENeAS, that will be deployed at the Met Office in 2024. RSEs have started revising the code to be faster and more efficient and begun collaborating with the Met Office to set the program up to run under the strict operational conditions on their HPC facilities.

Coding Case Study - CAIG Engagements

We worked closely with the Centre for AI in Government (CAIG) for two engagements that will be used as case studies developing the new Research Data Science Service.

Porting Large Language Models (LLMs) to Baskerville: In this engagement we coached researchers through the process of taking their existing LLM code and transferring it onto our GPU-accelerated Baskerville system. This involved meetings and remote coding sessions with the research group to work through the intricacies of getting code working on different architectures.

UN Speeches Website: This project involved importing UN Speeches from 1946 to the present day and building a website to explore the speeches. We implemented search and visualisation functionality and hosted the site on a dedicated VM on BEAR infrastructure here: [UN Speeches](#).

Throughout both engagements a Senior member of the RSG team held weekly progress catchups, where the researchers could discuss both progress and “process” to fit our agreement to demonstrate a model for the Research Data Science Service.

The RSG provided invaluable support in porting our large language models to the Baskerville system. Their expertise in optimising models for GPU environments helped improve training times and allowed us to scale up our research. The team's mentorship empowered our PhD student to become proficient in deploying AI models independently - an essential skill in modern Political Science.

Working with the RSG to build the UN speeches website was tremendously beneficial. Their ability to translate our research needs into a user-friendly web platform expanded public access to this unique dataset spanning decades of UN history. By delivering an engaging, interactive data discovery tool, the group's development work furthered the impact of our research beyond academia.

- **Professor Slava Jankin, School of Government and CAIG**

Coding Case Study - Particle Diffusion in Radiation Belts

Particle diffusion coefficients are a measure of how quickly particles spread out over time in a given medium. They are important for understanding a wide range of phenomena, including the transport of pollutants in the atmosphere, the spread of diseases and the propagation of radiation.

In this project, we implemented a cutting-edge numerical model to calculate particle diffusion coefficients for energetic charged particles in the magnetosphere. These particles can interact with satellites and with the Earth's atmosphere, causing a variety of effects, including auroras, geomagnetic storms and radiation hazards. Our goal is to improve the accuracy of the Space Weather forecasting models by understanding and including the effects that high-amplitude waves have on particle dynamics.

Working closely with the academic principal investigator, we have adopted a collaborative and efficient approach to software development, adhering to coding best practices. This collaborative spirit has fostered innovation and accelerated the progress of our project.

I couldn't speak more highly of the Research Software Group team that I have worked with. Fantastic communication before and during the project. And a high degree of professionalism with respect to the coding work performed: scientific and operational.

- **Dr Oliver Allanson, Space Environment & Radio Engineering (SERENE), School of Engineering**

Coding Case Study - Coulomb Crystals: Solving Lab problems with Artificial Intelligence

In December 2022, the Research Software Group were approached by Professor Tim Softley to solve a problem that was severely limiting the amount of data that could be extracted from their apparatus.

Professor Softley studies the fundamental processes of chemical bonding and kinetics using Coulomb Crystals. These crystals are a collection of a few hundred ionised atoms or molecules which have been cooled by lasers to about a thousandth of a degree above absolute zero, and trapped by an electric field in a vacuum chamber so they can be studied. Reactants are then targeted at the crystal and by examining how the fluorescing images of the crystal change with time, the reaction rate can be determined.

The problem we were asked to solve was to determine the number of atoms in an image of a pure crystal. This is a task that currently requires a researcher to make time-consuming comparisons between an experimental image and a library of simulated images.

After looking at conventional techniques, we opted to try using Deep Learning to interpret the number of atoms from an image. Initially, we used the University of Birmingham's Blue-BEAR HPC facility to simulate 700,000 images, before training our Deep Learning model.

This model has been packaged into software to be shared with international collaborators. Currently, results from this are encouraging and a paper is in progress.

The results of this work will have a major impact on our ability (and that of collaborators in Liverpool and Boulder, Colorado) to extract high quality data on reaction rates at extremely low temperatures from the experimental data. It will reduce the subjectivity of interpretation, improve the reproducibility of data, and dramatically speed up the process of image analysis, enhancing the opportunities for new scientific discoveries.

- **Professor Tim Softley, School of Chemistry, College of Engineering and Physical Sciences**

Rowland Seymour Case Studies

Rowland's research involves developing statistical tools to map and measure crimes, such as human trafficking and violence against women and girls. In one project the RSG helped to migrate a website that Rowland had previously developed and host it on a dedicated BEAR Cloud virtual machine. The website was developed using the Flask framework. The RSG helped to migrate the website and to make it compliant with accessibility requirements. This website has proved very useful for getting a more complete view of the risks of Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) in the UK and has been used by MPs to ask questions in Parliament. Thus far Rowland has used this website to collaborate on studies with three different councils in the UK, and is planning more in 2024.

The RSG is also developing a second website for Rowland's research, this time we are using the Django framework to allow social workers to access training materials about the impact of forced marriage.

Rowland has recently been awarded a prestigious Future Leaders Fellowship from UKRI, and we are very much looking forward to collaborating further on his continued research into modern slavery.

The BEAR software group were incredibly helpful in making sure the online survey tool was accessible and suitable for use. I didn't have any experience with hosting services before, so BEAR were able to make the website fully accessible and comply with legal and cookie policies from the University.

- **Dr Rowland Seymour, School of Mathematics**

Training

Carpentries Training

The Carpentries (<https://carpentries.org/>) lessons form an integral part of the training provision offered to University researchers. This training is provided by ARC, coordinated by REDG, and using a mix of instructors and helpers from within the RSG and from the wider research community at the University.

From the RSG, Gavin Yearwood, James Allsopp, James Carpenter, James Tyrrell, Jenny Wong, Jeremy Pike, Kamilla Kopec-Harding, Simon Branford, Simon Hartley and Warrick Ball are all qualified Carpentries instructors and between them have provided thirteen workshops covering Python, Git, R, and MATLAB in 2023. In addition, Adrian Dante Garcia, Cerys Lewis, and Makis Kappas have helped on Carpentries workshops this year.

Developing new courses

The RSG currently has three new courses under active development:

- **Advanced BlueBEAR** - A modular course to be tailored to each cohort's requirements. This course will explore advanced usage of BlueBEAR such as code compilation, advanced job configuration and containerisation. Expected first delivery in February 2024.
- **Intermediate Research Software Development** - Using Python as an example programming language to develop a core set of established, intermediate-level software development skills and best practices for working as part of a team in a research environment. Expected first delivery by February 2024.
- **Image Processing with Python** - A Data Carpentries course which will introduce the basics of image analysis using python and give researchers the skills they need to handle their own image data. Expected first delivery in February 2024.

In future years there is also potential for the development of an Intermediate R course and additional Data Carpentries focussing on specific fields such as Social Science, Geospatial Data or Genomics.

Intro to BlueBEAR

In 2023 we have taught the Introduction to BlueBEAR course 5 times. This course introduces users to BlueBEAR and other BEAR services where they learn how to navigate BEARAdmin,

load modules and submit a batch script. This year we moved the material from PowerPoint to Quarto, allowing the content to be more modular and tailored to our audience. Two of the courses were tailored to specific research groups (in Biosciences and Computational Chemistry).

- 100% found the mix of presentations and activities suitable and would recommend this training to colleagues
- Trainers were found to be:
 - “very knowledgeable”
 - Supportive
 - Friendly and enthusiastic
 - ‘super helpful!’ - Amy Webster PhD Bioscience

Machine Learning Workshop

In line with our ongoing commitment to foster cross-disciplinary collaboration and enhance the research capabilities of our university, we were delighted to conduct, in collaboration with Dr Dietmar Heinke, a one-day Machine Learning workshop for members of the Psychology department. The workshop, designed to introduce the fundamentals of Deep Learning, aimed to provide participants with a practical understanding of machine learning techniques.

The workshop took place at Elm House, home of the Institute for Interdisciplinary Data Science and AI, leveraging the Baskerville HPC cluster to provide each participant with access to a dedicated A100 GPU. This enabled participants to gain hands-on experience with Deep Learning frameworks and tools without the limitations of personal computing resources and ensured that they actively engaged with the material and gained a deeper understanding of the concepts.

The successful delivery of the Machine Learning workshop has had a significant impact on our university’s research community, opening up new avenues for interdisciplinary research using Deep Learning techniques. Additionally, it has provided Psychology department members with the skills and knowledge necessary to begin harnessing the power of Machine Learning in their research.

The trainers were very experienced with DNNs and excellent at answering questions throughout the whole workshop.

- **Machine Learning Workshop attendee**

Conferences and Events

BEAR Challenge

The annual BEAR Challenge returned again from 19 to 21 June with a record-breaking 50 participants. The participants were students from various taught programmes at the University. For 3 days the student teams went through 5 challenges using Baskerville - getting a variety of experience with the powerful GPUs on our supercomputer. The challenges covered a wide range of topics including navigating large datasets, using hash functions, image segmentation, agent based modelling and the Lenovo cluster challenge. Throughout the event there were career talks from NVIDIA, Lenovo and ARC.

The event concluded with a virtual tour of our dedicated research data centre, including the storage and the cutting edge direct water cooled supercomputers.

A blog post <https://blog.bham.ac.uk/bear/2023/08/03/bear-challenge-2023/> presents a day by day description of the event.

Feedback of the event was very positive with:

- 100% of responders enjoyed the BEAR Challenge
- 100% found the talks from NVIDIA and Lenovo interesting and engaging
- The venue was rated 4.86/5.0
- 71% said they would be interested in a career in HPC the other 29% said they were maybe interested
- 2 teams signed-up to the [CIUK 2023](#) cluster challenge

8th EasyBuild User Meeting

Four members of the BEAR Apps team (Chris, Gavin, James & Simon) travelled to Imperial College London in April 2023 to attend the 8th EasyBuild User Meeting. The annual EasyBuild User Meetings are a staple of the BEAR Apps Team's calendar, where the RSG have had a regular presence since 2019, with Simon Branford now also being on the organising committee.

Simon and James both presented at the event: Simon's talk was titled *EasyBuild 5.0 roadmap* and covered information on the future direction and plans of the EasyBuild framework whilst James spoke about the BEAR Portal service in a talk titled *BEAR Portal Apps: Open OnDemand interactive applications at University of Birmingham*.

It was a great opportunity to interact with other members of the EasyBuild community, particularly given the importance of the framework in the day-to-day maintenance of our HPC software stacks.

HPC-SIG

The High Performance Computing
Special Interest Group for UK Academia

The University of Birmingham has been a long-standing member and supporter of the HPC-SIG: The High Performance Computing Special Interest Group for UK Academia.

Members of the RSG (and the wider ARC) continue to support the HPC-SIG and regularly attend meetings. Simon Branford gave a talk at the Southampton meeting about *Open OnDemand* - the technology behind the popular *BEAR Portal* which ARC deployed in the early days of the pandemic to support researchers working remotely and continues to be widely used by University researchers.

In 2023 two RSG members served on the HPC-SIG Executive Committee:

- On 10 November 2022 Ed was appointed Chair of the HPC-SIG, nominated by Imperial and Warwick and seconded by Oxford. As Chair, Ed organised a meeting of many of the HPC- and Research Computing-related groups in UK academia, most of which are now listed on the [related groups](#) page on the website. The goal of the meeting was to raise awareness of the groups with each other, and to spark various collaborations between them. He also has focused this year on increasing the awareness of and interest in the general HPC-SIG meetings, with attendance increasing substantially in meetings in Southampton, Bath (our first hybrid meeting) and Cardiff. The programme of [future meetings](#) arranged at sites around the country further helps to present the (accurate!) image that the HPC-SIG is active and moving forwards. Ed chairs these HPC-SIG events, and has also spoken or led panels at all three meetings in 2023 (see [meeting reports](#)). Ed created and launched the new [HPC-SIG Mentoring Programme](#), where sysadmins are matched up with experienced mentors from other institutions. This is a first step in trying to address the national problem of a shortage of suitable sysadmins in research computing teams.
- Jenny also joined the [HPC-SIG Executive Committee](#) in 2023 as half of a shared EDIA Officer role. Jenny has helped shape the HPC-SIG's message around increasing diversity and was part of the team selecting the new branding and logo (as was James Carpenter as a very valuable volunteer!).

ISC & SC Conferences

Jenny contributed talks at two of the largest supercomputing conferences in the world this year: International Supercomputing (ISC), Hamburg, Germany, and Supercomputing (SC), Denver, US.

She participated in the [Women in HPC](#) program, a network that aims 'to promote, build and leverage a diverse and inclusive HPC workforce...' by delivering technical presentations about her work on the [DASP project](#). Jenny also championed the BEAR team and spoke about the state of UK RSE in the [RSE in HPC workshop at SC23](#), highlighting the vibrant networks that she has connected with such as RSE Midlands, UK RSE Society and HPC-SIG.

The conferences were also a fantastic opportunity to learn about the cutting-edge of HPC technologies and engage with leading international experts in the field. Following her positive experiences with the Women in HPC network, Jenny was later elected to the executive committee of the [HPC-SIG](#) HPC-SIG as an EDIA Officer.

RSE in Data and AI

Hosted by the University of Warwick in February this year, the [RSE in Data and AI Workshop](#) highlighted the contributions of those who facilitate data science and artificial intelligence research.

Jenny Wong delivered a walkthrough on "How to use the Baskerville Portal and the benefits it can provide to non-traditional HPC users". In this live demo, she described how OpenOnDemand, a piece of open-source software maintained by the Ohio Supercomputer Centre, allows users web access to HPC resources through the [Baskerville Portal](#). This lowers the barrier to accessing GPU compute for those who would like to run data science/ai workloads but are unfamiliar with traditional HPC and the command-line interface.

Jenny was also invited to sit on a panel about cloud versus local infrastructure, giving her perspectives from the HPC side of the debate. There was a very nuanced discussion that covered a range of topics such as which workloads were more suitable for cloud or HPC and how to provision the skills needed to support these workloads.

As a result of the workshop, Jenny later chaired an [N8 CIR](#) meeting about OpenOnDemand and hosted the University of York's RSE Team Lead for a 1-day visit to the RSG.

RSE Midlands

Annual Conference

The second [RSE Midlands](#) conference RSE Midlands 2023 was hosted by the Digital Research Service at the University of Nottingham on Monday the 24th of April 2023. The meeting included two sessions: the morning session on health data and the afternoon one on more general RSE topics. It continued on from the previous event: building a community, networking and showcasing the incredible breadth of skills RSEs in the Midlands possess. Lightning talks were given by RSG members: Warrick and Gavin.

Coding Club

The RSE Midlands Coding Club is a community for RSEs in the Midlands which hosts educational and informative presentations and workshops. On the 14th of June we ran a special Coding club event where guests from the National Center of Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) gave a series of presentations about RSE projects they have worked on in recent times. Attendees were able to take away lessons and advice and apply them to their own contexts.

A full list of topics covered by the NCSA and the rest of the topics presented this year can be found [here](#).

RSECon23

RSECon23 took place at Swansea University from September 5-7th, with eight ARC members attending the main conference or associated satellite events on September 4th and 8th. Warrick Ball presented a talk with thoughts on why researchers often re-invent small programs instead of collaborating to sustain and improve big ones, and a poster on the Journal of Open Source Software, where he is an editor. Makis Kappas contributed to the smooth running of the conference as a volunteer and Jenny Wong chaired the session on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.

Contact Us

Research Software Group

For information about the Research Software Group, see:

<https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/bear-software>

For any help with anything related to research software at the University of Birmingham please email bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk

BEAR / Advanced Research Computing

For information about BEAR, see:

<https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/bear>

For general help or information about any BEAR service (BlueBEAR HPC, Research Data Store, ...) contact the BEAR team by email at bearinfo@contacts.bham.ac.uk

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